

A LOW-COST, MINIMUM COMPLEXITY ALTITUDE/HEADING HOLD FLIGHT CONTROL SYSTEM

Aaron D. Kahn, ITT AES, Alexandria, Virginia

James C. Kellogg, US Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC

Abstract

For many one-way unmanned aerial vehicle payload delivery and remote sensing missions, the heading to the target location and local winds are known. For these missions, only altitude and heading hold features are needed. Further, because the vehicle will not be returning, minimizing cost is a priority. Due to the desire to reduce the physical size of the vehicle itself, the flight control system needs to be of minimal complexity to facilitate miniaturization. Presented is a prototype altitude/heading hold flight control system that has been developed for use in small, stable UAV platforms. Topics covered in this paper include system architecture, hardware, user interface, and preliminary test-flight results. A brief description of the miniature target aircraft, the Naval Research Laboratory's Micro Tactical Expendable (MITE), will be presented as a representation of the class of vehicle under consideration.

Nomenclature

<i>COTS</i>	Commercial-off-the shelf
<i>UAV</i>	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
<i>P</i>	Proportional Control
<i>PD</i>	Proportional-Derivative Control
<i>RC</i>	Radio Control
<i>I/O</i>	Input/Output
<i>PPM</i>	Pulse Position Modulation
<i>AGL</i>	Above Ground Level
<i>FCS</i>	Flight Control System

Introduction

There is a great desire to have small, autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to perform payload delivery and remote sensing

missions. These types of missions do not require the vehicles to return from the target area. To perform many of these missions, the heading to the target is known. Also, the local wind conditions are known. With these pieces of data, a resultant heading can be computed to allow the vehicle to fly towards the target area at a desired altitude. A major requirement for these missions is to have a low-cost, miniature, flight control system that can regulate both heading and altitude.

The result of that requirement is a system based on COTS sensors and components. An assumption is made that the vehicle itself is stable. This allows for the use of low performance sensors. Because only altitude and heading are to be regulated, basic flight control laws can be designed and implemented on a minimal computer. User interface to this type of system can be minimized to a simple menu-select system. To evaluate the performance and effectiveness of this type of miniature flight control system, a prototype has been constructed. Presented is the system architecture, hardware, user interface implemented, and preliminary flight-test results of this prototype. An overview of the final aircraft, the MITE is also included.

System Architecture

The architecture of the system focused on low-cost and miniaturization. The reason for this focus was to make the system compatible with small, disposable UAV aircraft. To help achieve these goals, it was assumed that the target vehicle would be statically stable. This resulted in the ability to use low-performance, low-cost sensors. Also, simple proportional (P) and proportional-derivative (PD) control laws could be implemented.

The system architecture is shown in Figure 1. Three main sensors are utilized in the design. A compass is needed to measure the vehicle heading

relative to magnetic north. A barometric altimeter is used for altitude measurement. A piezo yaw-rate gyro is implemented with the system to help damp any oscillations in the heading control loop. Both the altimeter and gyro signals are conditioned by op-amp circuits before being digitized by an A/D converted integrated into the microcontroller. The compass data is digital, and fed directly into the microcontroller. To permit manual flight of the vehicle during testing, a hobby radio control (RC) receiver is built into the system. The final control signals, whether generated from the control loops or manually from the RC receiver, are sent from the microcontroller to the servo actuators on the vehicle. The user interface is from a ground terminal and radio control transmitter. The terminal is for preflight parameter modification in the flight code on the microcontroller. The RC transmitter is for manual flight of the vehicle.

Figure 1. Flight Control System Architecture

Proportional and proportional-derivative control laws were used in this prototype. Two different control strategies were implemented. The first was a throttle-only system. This strategy assumes that the vehicle has two independently controller motors. Heading control is accomplished by differentially controlling the motors while altitude is regulated by collectively controlling the motors. The other strategy was a throttle-rudder method. Heading is controlled by the vehicle's rudder, and altitude is controlled by throttle. Both of these strategies were implemented on the system, and are user selectable. Figure 2 illustrates both of these control strategies.

Figure 2. Throttle-Only and Throttle-Rudder Control System Strategies

Hardware

As stated before, low-cost, low-performance sensors were to be used. Only a barometric altimeter, compass, and single rate gyro were needed, simplifying the overall design. The flight control computer was chosen to be a programmable microcontroller. Ground control system interface was designed for a RS-232 serial link. To allow for manual flight, a hobby radio control system was also designed into the system. Figure 3 illustrates the prototype flight control system and ground support hardware.

The sensors chosen for the prototype were the Motorola MPX4115A pressure sensor [1], the Vector 2X compass [2], and the Tokin CG-16DO piezo gyro [3]. Both the pressure sensor and the gyro have analog outputs. The compass is digital. To provide for more resolution in altitude, the pressure sensor output was conditioned with an op-amp circuit. This circuit cut off the unused range of the sensor, and amplified the desired region. The result of this conditioning is an altitude resolution of 3 feet and altitude range of about 1200 feet. The gyro output too was conditioned with an op-amp circuit. Besides amplifying the signal, it eliminates thermal drift errors in the gyro by utilizing the gyro reference output. To further condition the signals from these two sensors, a digital low-pass filter was implemented in the software. The compass is a two-axis magnetometer with a resolution of 1 degree. An attempt was made to minimize the

amount of ferrous metal in the proximity to the magnetometer. Data from the compass is sent via synchronous serial protocol.

The microcontroller chosen for the prototype was Microchip Technology's PIC 16F877 [4]. This microcontroller has an 8-channel 10-bit A/D converter, flash EEPROM, 3 timers, serial port, and numerous digital I/O lines. The clock speed of the 16F877 is 20MHz. Software development was done in C utilizing the PICC[®] compiler [5].

For manual override, a hobby radio control system was built into the flight control system (FCS). A Hitec 555 receiver was modified so that only the pulse position modulation (PPM) signal sent from the transmitter is passed onto the microcontroller. The purpose for this modification

was to reduce the resources required on the PIC to interface with the receiver. During flight, the user has the ability to disengage the FCS with one of the switches on the transmitter. While the FCS is flying the vehicle, the RC system is used to bias the control laws to the current trim position for the aircraft. This allows for in-flight trim adjustments while the FCS is operating.

To provide for in-field adjustments to the controller and change the altitude and heading commands a ground terminal was designed into the architecture. For the prototype a Hewlett Packard HP-48G calculator was used. Flight controller gains and commands are stored in flash EEPROM resident on the microcontroller.

Figure 3. Prototype Flight Control System and Ground Hardware

User Interface

It was desired to have a user interface with the prototype system in order to change flight control parameters during the test phase. This interface

would also allow for modification of the altitude and heading commands. To provide for this interface, the flight control system hardware was chosen to allow for RS-232 serial communications.

To minimize the complexity of the code, which has to fit into the limited resources of the PIC, a menu-select system was implemented. The menu displays the current settings stored in memory, the current heading, and a numbered list of the adjustable values. Figure 4 shows what the menu looks like on a terminal screen. The user first selects the desired value field. The program then prompts the user for the new value. Once this new value has been entered, the program saves it to flash memory and exits. Entry into the menu was programmed to be interrupt controlled.

Figure 4. Screen Shot of the User Interface Menu

Preliminary Flight-Test Results

The prototype flight control system seen in Figure 3, which has not yet been miniaturized, was test-flown on a surrogate aircraft to evaluate the performance of the altitude, and heading-hold control loops. A Multiplex Smiley, an off-the-shelf electric model airplane, was utilized for the tests. The aircraft in flight, with the prototype flight control system can be seen in Figure 5. Due to the limited resources on the PIC microcontroller, no flight data was recorded. Instead, visual observations were made and the controller gains were adjusted experimentally.

A total of four flights were made to evaluate the performance and tune the flight control system. The first two flights were for tuning the heading-hold control loop gains. The commanded heading for the tests was the centerline heading of an airfield runway. Heading hold was observed to be within 10 degrees of the commanded heading using the differential throttle control method. The

controller was engaged at different off-axis angles, and was found to have good recovery up to off-axis angles of 90 degrees from commanded heading.

The third flight was to test the altitude control loop. Results were not conclusive for this test. A command of approximately 50 feet AGL was given. With initial conditions of both above and below the target altitude, the aircraft was observed to neither descend nor ascend to the target altitude. Ground testing verified that the control loop was indeed working, and responding to sensor input. It is suspected that the poor power to weight ratio of the aircraft was to blame for the problem.

The final flight was again a heading control test to verify once more the performance of that channel.

Final results of these tests showed promising performance in the heading control loop, yet more tests are needed to verify performance of the altitude loop. Towards this end, a new surrogate test aircraft has been built to provide better performance in order to further test the altitude control loop.

Figure 5. Multiplex Smiley Aircraft with Prototype Hardware Attached

The MITE

The intended UAV platform for the final miniaturized flight control system is the Naval Research Laboratory's Micro Tactical Expendable (MITE). MITE is designed to be the smallest practical aircraft that can perform useful missions for the Navy and Marine Corps. Over-the-hill reconnaissance, battle damage assessment, and electronic warfare are some of its possible uses. A

14-inch wingspan MITE, equipped with a video camera and transmitter, successfully demonstrated low-and-slow reconnaissance in November 1999.

The MITE configuration, a low-aspect-ratio flying wing powered by twin electric motors, is optimized for low Reynolds number flight. The propellers counter rotate to cancel torque effects for easier hand launching. The propellers' slipstream flows over most of the wing and control surface area, enhancing low speed lift and control. By mounting the propellers at the wingtips and setting their rotation to counteract the wingtip vortices, drag is reduced through the Zimmerman effect. The payload, located in the nose between the

propellers, has an unobstructed forward view. MITE is an inherently stable airplane.

The present MITE airframes consist of a balsa framework with a polyester fiber covering similar to traditional flying model airplane construction. Maximum use is made of COTS components, including coreless DC electric motors and reductions gearboxes, RC hobby servos, and both lithium sulfur dioxide (single use) and lithium ion (rechargeable) batteries. The 18.5-inch wingspan MITE shown in Figure 6 weighs between 7.5 and 9 ounces, depending on the flight battery used. The current vehicle is capable of supporting an additional 3.5 ounces of payload. Maximum endurance is approximately 20 minutes.

Figure 6. MITE in Flight

Conclusion

For many one-way, UAV payload delivery and remote-sensing missions, it is desired to have a low-cost flight control system. For these types of missions altitude and heading control is all that is needed. To test this concept, a prototype system has been developed. This system implements low-cost hardware with a minimum of

hardware/software complexity. It allows for quick development and testing through its radio control and menu user interface. Future miniaturization of the system is possible because of the use of low-performance sensors and microcontroller. Currently the system is under further flight-testing and evaluation.

References

[1] Motorola Semiconductor, Integrated Silicon Pressure Sensor for Manifold Absolute Pressure, Altimeter or Barometric Applications On-Chip Signal Conditioned, Temperature Compensated and Calibrated, Motorola Semiconductor Technical Data, MPX4115A/D, Oct 2001

[2] Precision Navigation, Vector 2X and 2XG Electronic Compass Modules, Complete App Notes, 2X, Oct 2001

[3] Tokin, Ceramic Gyro, Data Sheet, CG-16DO, Oct 2001.

[4] Microchip Technology INC., PIC16F87X Data Sheet, 28/40-Pin 8-Bit CMOS FLASH Microcontrollers, DS30292A 5K, Nov 1998.

[5] Custom Computer Services INC., PIC C Compiler, Reference Manual PCB, PCM, PCH, and PCW, Jul 2001.